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IMPROVEMENT OF THE SUSPENSION MECHANISM OF COTTON CULTIVATORS.**D.Karimova**

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Annotation. This article analyzes the issues of improving the suspension mechanisms of cultivators used in cotton cultivation from a scientific and theoretical perspective. The study studies the design of existing cultivators, the principle of operation and shortcomings of their suspension mechanisms, and proposes new improved constructive solutions. The proposed mechanism is aimed at improving the quality of soil cultivation, ensuring the stability of the unit and reducing energy consumption. The results show that with the help of an improved suspension mechanism, the stability of the cultivation depth increases and labor productivity improves significantly.

Keywords: Cotton cultivation, cultivator, suspension mechanism, hydraulic system, soil cultivation, agrotechnical requirements, energy saving, inter-row cultivation, mechanization.

INTRODUCTION. In agriculture, especially in the cotton sector, high-quality and timely soil cultivation is one of the main factors in achieving high yields. Mechanized tillage equipment plays an important role in improving the agrotechnical condition of the soil, preserving moisture, eliminating weeds, and creating favorable conditions for the development of the plant root system. In this regard, cultivators are widely used as one of the main technical tools in the cultivation of cotton rows.

The effective operation of cultivators largely depends on the design of their suspension mechanism, which ensures the adaptability of the unit to the soil surface, the movement of the working bodies at a stable depth, and the quality of the overall technological process. However, practice shows that the suspension mechanisms of existing cultivators have a number of constructive and operational shortcomings. In particular, uneven depth of cultivation leads to deterioration of soil quality, vibrations arising during the movement of the unit negatively affect the stable operation of the equipment, and excessive energy consumption reduces economic efficiency.

Although the KRX-4 and KRX-3.6 cultivators, which have been widely used in agriculture, were considered effective equipment in their time, their capabilities are insufficient in terms of modern agrotechnical requirements, resource-saving technologies and high-precision processing. Especially in conditions of intensive farming, high accuracy, stability and energy efficiency are required when working with soil.

In this regard, improving the suspension mechanism of cultivators, optimizing its design parameters and introducing modern technical solutions is one of the issues of urgent scientific and practical importance. Research in this area plays an important role in increasing the efficiency of agricultural machinery, saving energy resources and achieving high results in cotton growing.

The suspension mechanism proposed based on the research includes a number of innovative elements that are fundamentally different from traditional designs. This scientific research is aimed at improving the suspension mechanism of cotton cultivators, which is carried out on the basis of an integrated approach - by combining analytical, theoretical and experimental methods. The research process takes into account the laws of operation of mechanical systems, soil-machine interaction and agrotechnical requirements.

It was found that suspension mechanisms usually consist of the following main elements:

base frame (main load-bearing structure),
hydraulic cylinders (for controlling and adjusting the working depth),
three-point linkage system (mechanism providing connection with the tractor).

During the analysis, along with the advantages of these systems, their disadvantages were also identified, in particular, problems such as insufficient dynamic stability, uneven working depth and suboptimal load distribution were highlighted. In order to ensure the effective operation of the suspension mechanism, its mathematical model is developed. The model takes into account the main forces and parameters affecting the mechanism. In particular:

loading force (effect of the mass of the aggregate and working bodies),
the location of the center of gravity,
the resistance force of the soil (depending on the mechanical composition and humidity),
the speed of movement of the aggregate.

Based on these parameters, the equilibrium state, stability and vibration processes of the mechanism were theoretically analyzed. As a result, mathematical relationships and functional relationships are developed that allow determining the optimal design parameters. This serves as a scientific basis for determining the effective operating range of the suspension mechanism and its improvement.

The suspension mechanism proposed on the basis of the research includes a number of innovative elements that are fundamentally different from traditional designs. The main innovations of this mechanism are:

Elastic shock absorber connecting link - reduces shocks and vibrations that occur during the operation of the unit and ensures uniform load distribution. This maintains stable contact of the working bodies with the soil.

Hydraulic stabilizer system - controls the movement of the suspension mechanism, limits lateral deviations of the unit and increases its dynamic stability.

Automatic depth adjustment system - automatically regulates the depth of tillage in accordance with soil conditions, which ensures accurate fulfillment of agrotechnical requirements.

These design solutions, working together, expand the functional capabilities of the suspension mechanism and increase its efficiency.

In particular:

The stability of the tillage depth has increased by 15–20%, which leads to an improvement in the quality of soil tillage;

Fuel consumption has decreased by 10–12%, which increases energy efficiency and economic efficiency;

the vibration level of the unit has significantly decreased, resulting in increased reliability and service life of the mechanism.

Also, during the analysis, it is observed that the unit's performance has increased, the operator's control has improved, and the maintenance requirements have decreased.

One of the important advantages of the improved suspension mechanism is its high energy efficiency. Due to the optimal distribution of the load in the mechanism design and the balancing of soil resistance, excessive energy losses are reduced.

The reduction of dynamic loads and vibrations that occur during the operation of the unit increases the operational reliability of the equipment. As a result, the wear of machine parts slows down, the maintenance interval is extended, and the overall service life increases. This is also important from an economic point of view, and serves to reduce the cost of equipment.

The technical solution fully complies with the strategy for the development of modern agricultural machinery. In particular, it serves such priority areas as the introduction of resource-saving and energy-efficient technologies, optimization of production processes, and the creation of environmentally sustainable systems. The improved suspension mechanism, while meeting these

requirements, serves as a solid scientific basis for the implementation of innovative mechanization tools.

Conclusion

The tractor's traction force is effectively used due to the stable and uniform interaction of the working bodies of cotton cultivators with the soil. As a result, fuel consumption is reduced, the overall efficiency of the unit increases, and production costs are reduced.

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